

Effect of Poll Everywhere E-Learning on Students' Anxiety and Achievement in Economics Among Undergraduates at a Public University

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Abstract

This research determined the effect of the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform on students' exams anxiety academic achievement in Economics in Cross River State, Nigeria. Three null hypotheses were developed in accordance with the particular research goals that led the research. One control group and one treatment group were used in this quasi-experimental investigation. The participants in this research were all full-time normal students studying Education Economics at the University of Calabar's Department of Social Science Education in Calabar, Nigeria. A sample of 328 students who possess cellphones was chosen from the population using a purposeful selection method. Data was collected using the Test-Anxiety Inventory (Spielberger, 1980), which had reliability coefficients of 0.96, 0.91, and 0.91 for three subscales, and the Economics Achievement Test (EAT), which had a reliability value of 0.795. An independent t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses. Findings indicate that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform has a considerable effect on students' exams anxiety and academic performance in Economics. It was concluded that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform might be utilized effectively to educate and assess students studying Economics and other relevant subjects. This can be accomplished by developing and integrating course modules using the Poll Everywhere online platform.

Keywords: Academic achievement, exams anxiety, Economics, e-learning, poll everywhere, undergraduates.

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Introduction

Economics is one of the most important subjects in social sciences because it considers the day-to-day activities of households, firms, and the economic situation in the entire nation. This vital subject brings to fore the problems facing humans and the need to make rational decisions towards improving cost-effectiveness, profit maximization, social inclusion, welfare, and marginal social productivity. Individuals studying Economics at the secondary or tertiary level were expected to demonstrate dedication and be studious to improve their academic performance and experience additional advantages associated with the study of Economics.

The academic performance of students in Economics has dropped dramatically in recent years, causing worry among stakeholders. According to careful observation, many undergraduates studying Education Economics perform similarly to their peers in the Economics Major. Students in the past have complained about the complexity surrounding Economics courses, particularly those that require mathematics and statistics. As a result of their fear of mathematics, they have performed badly in the subject. This explanation, however, has been dismissed since students' performance in other Economics courses that do not include mathematics has not differed. This led the researchers to believe that low academic performance among Economics students is waning across all classes. Several studies have been commissioned to address comparable issues, with a variety of suggestions given at various periods and locations (Adu, Tadu, & Eze, 2012; Ganyaupfu, 2014; Effiom & Bassey, 2018; Owan & Ekaette, 2019; Bassey, Owan, & Agunwa, 2019).

Scholars and researchers have identified many variables as correlates of student academic success in the literature. School management issues (Owan, Nwannunu, & Madukwe, 2018), school leadership behavior (Tatlah, Iqbal, Amin, & Quraishi, 2014), students' disability status (Lagoke, Komolafe, Ige, & Oladejo, 2010), students' perception of discipline (Offem, Arop, & Owan, 2019), teacher demographics representation (Holt & Gershenson, 2015), and the management and use (Arop, Agunwa, & Owan, 2019; Owan & Robert, 2019). Other studies have identified factors affecting student performance as class attendance, age, learning styles or preferences, gender, class size, entry qualifications, family income, students' perceptions, poor student discipline, students' attitudes, teachers' qualifications, the school physical environment, and school leadership (Haist, Wilson, Elam, Blue, & Fosson, 2000; Aripin, Mahmood, Rohaizad, Yeop, & Anuar, 2008; Heinesen, 2010; Mlambo, 2011; Owan, 2012; Ali, Haider, Munir, Khan, & Ahmed, 2013; Ehiane, 2014; Owan & Ekpe, 2019).

This study, on the other hand, examines students' exams anxiety as a factor that may influence their performance. This is because, although many students have little or no reasons for their low performance in Economics, others have connected it to their fear of the topic as a difficult subject that leads them to lose confidence while preparing for or taking examinations. Such a lack of confidence may increase their nervousness while taking Economics exams, and as a result, their academic performance may suffer. According to Owan, Etudor-Eyo, and Esuong (2019), exams anxiety is a psychological concept that describes an individual's emotional state before completing a task. Students' exams anxiety may stem from fear or a misperception of the job at hand (Owan et al., 2019). As a consequence of the above statement, exams anxiety is a strong and troubling feeling that students all over the world experience while taking exams. Many college students suffer from exams anxiety, which may have a long-term detrimental effect on their performance and comfort (Hanem, 2016). Exam's anxiety has been shown to have an effect on students' academic performance (Owan, 2012; Shuaibu, Surajo, & Muhammadi, 2017; Effiom & Bassey, 2018; Owan et al., 2019).

The prevalence and correlates of exams anxiety were investigated by Bhatta, Subba, and Bhandary (2018). According to the study's results, 76.3 percent of students experienced

exams anxiety. Furthermore, private school students reported much greater exams anxiety than government school students. Additionally, sex, family type, academic achievement desire, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and adjustment had no effect on exams anxiety. Overall exams anxiety and grade point average show a statistically significant negative connection, according to Hanem (2016)'s results (P.01). According to the results, exams anxiety has a significant and efficient impact on nursing students' performance. Children with high levels of exams anxiety should be recognized and treated in order to enhance their academic performance, it was recommended. Another study discovered a significant relationship between adolescent exams anxiety and academic performance ($r = -0.23$, $p = .000$) (Yousefi, Talib, Mansor, Juhari, Redzuan, 2010).

Owan et al. (2019) examined the use of punishment, students' exams anxiety, and mathematics performance in secondary schools in Cross River State. Administration of punishment has a significant impact on students' exams anxiety and mathematics performance; administration of punishment has a significant impact on students' exams anxiety and mathematics performance; administration of punishment has a significant impact on students' exams anxiety and mathematics performance. Toward the close of the twenty-first century, a number of technological dynamics emerged, with different e-learning platforms being developed to help students study more effectively. These gains are due to the fact that e-learning platforms allow for more hands-on activities, decrease the fear of addressing teachers, and diminish shyness and disciplinary problems that are common in traditional classrooms. Coldwell, Craig, Paterson, and Mustard, to use their terms (2008),

online learning environments (OLEs) facilitate learning by utilising software that enables the design, delivery, and management of online teaching and learning. The notion of providing courses wholly online is relatively new and allows students of diverse backgrounds and in geographically dispersed locations to have access to, and participate in, the same courses. In the past, students have been able to study 'off-campus', or from a distance, relying on study guides, detailed notes, and textbooks, but with few or no opportunities for interaction or collaboration. OLEs provide these resources but additionally, they enable regular interaction and collaboration between students and instructors through the use of discussion boards, chat rooms, and other interactive functionality, bringing all students into a 'virtual classroom'. The key difference between traditional off-campus and online is the ability for students to communicate and collaborate via the OLE, reducing the effects and limitations of isolation (p. 19).

In general, the importance of E-learning cannot be overstated, and this study presents a new E-learning platform dubbed "Poll Everywhere." Poll Everywhere is an online classroom and audience system that may be used to educate and assess students in the same manner as a conventional classroom. This platform was founded in April 2007 by Sean Eby, Jeff Vyduna, and Brad Gessler, with headquarters in San Francisco, California. This seems to be the first study to examine the effect of the poll anywhere online platform on exams anxiety and academic performance among Economics students. E-learning, on the other hand, has been

shown to have a significant effect on students' exams anxiety in studies (Alkhalaf, Drewa, & Alhussain, 2012; Bauk, 2015; Harandi, 2015).

The research of Owan et al. (2020) found that the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has a substantial impact on students' exams anxiety because students who were taught utilizing Poll Everywhere eLearning had less exams anxiety than those who were taught using the conventional method. It was also shown that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform has a substantial impact on students' academic achievement in Economics. Students that were taught utilizing the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform outperformed those in the control group in Mathematics. Yazdi and Zandkarimi (2013) evaluated students' achievement motivation and exams anxiety at the beginning and end of their educational term, providing pre-test and post-test ratings. The results indicated that e-learning in the present location, with teachers working remotely and parents participating virtually, was more effective than the control group. It led to a reduction in exams anxiety, as well as an improvement in achievement motivation and academic performance among high school pupils.

E-learning has also been shown to improve students' academic success in their courses. Zare, Sarikhani, Salari, and Mansouri (2016), for example, found that students in the experimental group scored statistically substantially higher on the evaluated knowledge and creative factors. The study discovered that e-learning helps chemistry students learn more and be more creative, and that additional e-learning alternatives for a wider audience should be made accessible. Similarly, Tossy (2017) found a strong link between student confidence in e-learning systems and student achievement. The academic achievement of the two groups of students was compared by Thabet and Kalyankar (2014). The results of the research revealed a significant increase in achievement and that EL is more efficient than traditional learning in terms of (remembering, understanding, and applying) skills. Mutendwahothe (2013) looked at the impact of e-Learning on the academic achievement of students and instructors. The results of the research revealed that e-Learning had a significant effect on student performance, with student-teachers who were taught using e-Learning consistently outperforming student-teachers who were taught using the traditional method. Students' confidence in e-learning systems was shown to be favorably linked with their academic achievement in another study (Kisanjara, Tossy, Sife & Msanjila, 2017).

As a result of the above, numerous researches conducted across the world have tried to address students' academic performance by combining it with various independent variables. Exam exams anxiety and e-learning have also been investigated by academics. E-learning studies, in particular, have failed to acknowledge the e-learning platforms used in trials. As a result, the focus has been on e-learning in general. This research is unusual in that it aims to concentrate more precisely on the "Poll Everywhere" e-learning platform to see the effect it has on students' exams anxiety and academic performance in Economics while bridging the gaps on the lack of research on e-learning in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The specific purpose of this study is to assess:

- i. The effect of Poll Everywhere E-learning platform on students' exams anxiety.
- ii. The effect of Poll Everywhere E-learning platform on students' academic performance in Economics.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

- i. Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has no significant effect on students' exams anxiety.
- ii. Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has no significant effect on students' academic performance in Economics.

Methods

A quasi-experimental design was used in this investigation, including one control group and one treatment group. The participants in this research were all full-time normal students studying Education Economics at the University of Calabar's Department of Social Science Education in Calabar, Nigeria. This group included students in their first to final year who possess a smartphone. These pupils were recognized according to their grade level throughout their separate lectures. The permission of the instructor was secured, and students using smartphones were requested to raise their hands. As a result, it was simple to get their phone numbers for participation in a WhatsApp group created just for this research. Students who possess cellphones but were absent from class were included using a snowball technique with the help of their peers. A total of 202 pupils were ultimately chosen for the research.

Two instruments were used: a 20-item Test-Anxiety Inventory (TAI) created by Spielberger in 1980 and an Economics Achievement Test (EAT), designed by the researchers following a review of literature. The Anxiety Inventory is a four-point Likert scale on which students must choose one of four options: (1) Almost Never, (2) Occasionally, (3) Frequently, and (4) Almost Always are the four options. The alpha coefficient reliability values for subscales of the original Anxiety Inventory were 0.96 for TAI-T, 0.91 for TAI-W, and 0.91 for TAI-E. (Spielberger, 1980). The EAT was used to assess students' academic achievement.

The sample of respondents for the research was carefully split into control and treatment groups, with each group consisting of 101 students. The control group received conventional instruction on an economics subject, whereas the treatment group received instruction on the same topic through the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform. The Anxiety Inventory (TAI) and the Economics Achievement Test (EAT) were given to the students in the control group after the exercise using the Paper and Pencil Approach (PPA). The treatment group received the

identical TAI and EAT instruments through the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform. Participants in both groups answered appropriately to the items, and all of the administered copies of the instruments were collected and collated after the exercise. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and the null hypotheses were evaluated with independent t-tests. In the next part, the findings of the analysis are reported.

Results

Hypothesis one

Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has no significant effect on students' exams anxiety. This null hypothesis was tested using independent t-test based on the exams anxiety data collected from the treatment and control groups. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Independent t-test results summary showing the effect of Poll Everywhere E-learning platform and students' exams anxiety

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	Sig.
Exam's anxiety	Treatment	101	20.06	6.042	16.149*	.000
	Control	101	44.50	12.608		

*Significant at the .01 level; Df = 200; Mean difference = 24.44

According to the findings in Table 1, students in the treatment group had lower exams anxiety mean scores than their peers in the control group. This indicates that students who were taught using conventional techniques had greater exams anxiety than students who were taught using the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform, with a mean difference of 24.44 At 200 degrees of freedom, the p-value of .000 is less than the .05 alpha threshold. The null hypothesis was rejected as a consequence of this finding, but the alternative hypothesis was kept. As a result, the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has a substantial impact on exams anxiety among students.

Hypothesis two

The Poll Everywhere E-learning platform has no substantial impact on students' economic academic achievement. Based on students' performance in the EAT from both the treatment and control groups, this hypothesis was evaluated using an independent t-test. Table 2 shows the outcome of the investigation.

Table 2: Independent t-test results summary showing the effect of Poll Everywhere E-learning platform and students' academic performance in Economics.

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	Sig.
Academic Performance in Economics	Treatment	101	11.25	1.163	12.011*	.000
	Control	101	4.10	1.200		

*Significant at the .01 level; df = 200; Mean difference = 7.15

The findings, as shown in Table, show that the treatment group's average academic performance in Economics was greater than that of the control group. This indicates that students who were taught using the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform did better on the Economics Achievement Test (EAT) than students who were taught using conventional techniques. The p-value of .000 is smaller than the alpha level of .05 at 200 degrees of freedom, according to a quick examination. The null hypothesis was rejected as a consequence of this finding, indicating that the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform had a substantial impact on students' academic achievement in Economics.

Discussion

The study's first result revealed that the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform had a substantial impact on exams anxiety among students. When students were taught utilizing the Poll Everywhere eLearning method, exams anxiety was lower than when they were taught using the conventional way. Because users of the Poll Everywhere site are separated from others, including their instructors, this result may have emerged in this manner. As a result, the dread imposed by their colleagues who may communicate their concerns for the exams is reduced, making listening colleagues fearful as well. Students' self-confidence may be enhanced if they know there will be no supervisor there and no one to speak to while taking the exams in the comfort of their own homes or a convenient place. This conclusion supports the findings of previous research (Alkhalaf, Drewa, & Alhussain, 2012; Bauk, 2015; Harandi, 2015), all of which found a link between eLearning and exams anxiety in students. According to Yazdi and Zandkarimi (2013), e-learning at the current site with instructors Teleworking and virtual presence of parents was more successful than the control group.

The study's second result revealed that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform had a substantial impact on students' economics academic achievement. Students who were taught using the Poll Everywhere E-learning platform outperformed those who were taught using conventional teaching techniques on the Economics Achievement Test (EAT). This result is expected, given that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform has already been shown to decrease exams anxiety and increase self-confidence. The fact that the Poll Everywhere platform reduces and boosts exams anxiety and self-confidence may be one of the reasons why students' academic performance increases. This conclusion is consistent with Zare, Sarikhani, Salari, and Mansouri (2016), who found that students in the experimental group scored significantly better on the assessed variables of knowledge and creativity. The research found that e-learning is beneficial for students' knowledge and creative acquisition, and that more e-learning possibilities for a broader audience should be made available. Similarly, Tossy (2017) discovered a positive significant connection between student trust in e-learning systems and student success. Thabet and Kalyankar (2014) found that the EL has attained efficiency higher than conventional learning in (remembering, understanding, and application) abilities, with a substantial improvement in accomplishment. Furthermore, Mutendwahothe (2013) demonstrated that e-Learning had a substantial impact on student performance, as student-

teachers who were taught using e-Learning consistently outperformed student-teachers who were taught using the conventional approach. Another research found that students' trust in e-learning systems had a favorable correlation with their academic performance (Kisanjara, Tossy, Sife & Msanjila, 2017).

Conclusion

The results of this research led to the conclusion that the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform may be utilized to effectively educate and assess learners in Economics and other behavioural sciences. Students' exams anxiety is reduced, and their academic performance in Economics is improved, thanks to the Poll Everywhere platform. In general, it was shown that students' exams anxiety and their academic achievement in Economics are inversely related.

Recommendations

The following suggestions were made based on the findings of this study:

- i. Every Nigerian institution should use the Poll Everywhere eLearning platform to educate and train students in order to enhance their comprehension and academic achievement.
- ii. Before evaluating internet facilities at the school, the government and university administration should verify that there are open wireless networks that do not demand any kind of subscription from professors or students. Staff and students will be able to utilize the Poll Everywhere eLearning tool without interruption.
- iii. Teachers should get refresher training on how to utilize the Poll Everywhere app or website. This may be accomplished via seminars or workshops that teach people how to utilize the eLearning platform effectively.
- iv. As an eLearning platform, the Poll Everywhere application or website should be used to assess students' skills and during exams in order to decrease exams anxiety and, as a result, academic performance.
- v. Psychology and counseling specialists should be engaged in sufficient numbers to aid in the reduction of students' exams anxiety prior to the start of any examination. This will aid in the preparation of such students for exams and will help them to enhance their academic performance.

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